
Open Access eBook Data Trust

Legal Agenda

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Executive Summary

The Open Access eBook Data Trust is a collaborative project funded by the Andrew W. Mellon Foundation. The project is international in scope, and project partners include BISG, Curtin University, Educopia, and University of North Texas. The goal of the project is to create a Data Trust to track, analyze, and communicate open access (OA) ebook usage data and to develop tools that tell a compelling story of use and engagement to funders, publishers, and authors.¹

This report proceeds in two parts: Part I advises on international data protection and privacy laws relevant to the Data Trust; Part II considers the advantages and disadvantages of various legal structures for the Data Trust. Together, these sections inform the grant narrative's promise to "define the governance and architecture for the data trust and articulate the resulting priorities for development of the technical architecture." This report also provides recommendations on where the Data Trust should incorporate and which entity form to adopt.²

The Open Data Institute defines a *data trust* as "a legal structure that provides independent stewardship of data."³ Creating a legal framework of the data trust concept that applies to the challenge of ebook usage turns on the critical issue of trust. Some of the major issues that the OA ebook Data Trust must deal with to engender trust include:

- Balancing the interests and incentives of a variety of stakeholders in the OA ebook ecosystem;
- Involving both commercial and nonprofit stakeholders in the project;
- Mitigating antitrust concerns and the risk of revealing commercially sensitive information;
- Maintaining independence in the role of creating open, community-defined standards for usage data and data exchange from any particular metrics service provider or publisher; and
- Enhancing transparency and incentivizing innovation and partnership.

A specific legal structure will not solve all of these issues, but it will ameliorate them. Strong governance frameworks, adoption of ethical standards, solid technical security, relationship building with diverse stakeholders, education of the data trust concept and purpose, and development of superior products and services will also sustain the Data Trust.

A well-structured privacy program and a privacy by design approach will also enable the Data Trust to meet its compliance burden on an international scale. While an all-encompassing analysis of the regulatory obligations in every prospective member territory is not a feasible undertaking at this stage,

¹ OA Usage Trust Final Report

² While the law surrounding legal entities varies geographically, the entity recommendations provided herein are grounded in US law.

³ Open Data Institute

this report does cover four key jurisdictions where one or more partners are located: the United Kingdom, the United States, Netherlands, and Australia.

1.0 Recommendations

1.1 Entity Recommendation

This report recommends structuring the Data Trust as a two-part legal entity that conceptually, technically, legally, financially, and organizationally separates the roles of collective management of open data and open standards from collectively-operated data or analytics services.⁴ This recommendation veers away from the concept of a centralized Data Trust and entertains a decentralized structure that was discussed by Delacroix and Lawrence (2019).⁵

Legally, this can be accomplished in a variety of ways, however this report recommends two different frameworks:

- Adopt a Parent-Subsidiary legal structure whereby the nonprofit parent provides an independent governance structure for developing OA ebook standards and a benefit corporation subsidiary that sells ebook usage data and analytics services; or
- Incorporate the Data Trust as a single entity (nonprofit or benefit corporation)⁶ and become a subsidiary under an existing nonprofit that has an international focus, such as OAPEN. In this example, the Data Trust subsidiary would offer ebook usage data and analytics services, and OAPEN would manage collective governance and open data standards (or vice versa).

For the reasons discussed in section 13, the two-part entity structure is recommended as it achieves the Data Trust's core objectives, while supporting its proposed business model and addressing stakeholder concerns regarding independence between open standards creation and data services.

An alternate entity model is also offered in case a centralized model is preferred by stakeholders, or if the types of data analytics services sold by the Data Trust are not classified as unrelated business tax income (UBTI). This alternate recommendation is that the Data Trust be incorporated as a nonprofit or

⁴This recommendation is in alignment with opinions expressed by Open Book Publishers (OPB).

⁵ Delacroix and Lawrence, *Bottom-up Data Trusts* ("One can imagine an ecosystem of Trusts where one Trust A specializes in direct data management (possibly choosing to locate its servers in a specific jurisdiction), while Trust B devolves responsibility for data management to Trust A. Trust B would then focus on the policy, rather than the practicalities, underlying data sharing. This would allow trustees to focus on the use to which the data is put rather than the detailed mechanisms of access and storage which would be standardized.")

⁶This would depend on UBTI.

merge with an existing nonprofit that is engaged in complementary activities, such as OAPEN, to benefit from shared resources and privacy expertise.

1.2 Recommendation - Privacy Compliance and Preferred Jurisdiction for Incorporation

While international regulatory compliance is a significant factor in deciding where to incorporate the Data Trust, it should not be the guiding factor. Tradeoffs exist between the burden of regulatory compliance, the advantages of a particular country's case law and legal system, and other factors. The Data Trust can best comply with a patchwork of international regulations by taking a risk-based approach and prioritize meeting the privacy obligations of the strictest jurisdiction, such as the European Union. In doing so, compliance with less prescriptive privacy regimes becomes an easier task for the Data Trust. An alternative solution is to outsource regulatory compliance obligations to a third party service provider.

The preferred country to incorporate the Data Trust is the Netherlands. Australia is noted as a good alternative. Factors which influenced this decision include: (1) the country's legal system and relevant case law; (2) data privacy regime; (3) privacy compliance risks; (4) copyright; (5) database rights; (6) location of project staff; (7) location of IT infrastructure and physical servers; (8) data localization requirements; and (9) tax considerations. The major advantages to incorporating in the Netherlands include the availability of *sui generis* database rights, the maturity of the European privacy framework, and the proximity to other major OA partners. The major advantages of incorporating in Australia include a stable privacy framework with possible exemptions for the Data Trust, location of a large base of project staff, and the location of the project's technical infrastructure.

2.0 Definitions

For the purpose of this report the following definitions apply:

- Data trust is defined as '[a legal structure that provides independent stewardship of data.](#)'
- Data Trust is the Open Access eBook Usage Data Trust project.
- Data providers are publishers, platforms, people, communities or other organizations that make data available to the Data Trust directly or through third-party data providers.
- Data users are the primary users of data collected and stored by the Data Trust, who use the data for the purpose for which it was gathered, such as for OA ebook usage data and analytics. Data users might include funders, publishers, authors, or, collectively, Data Trust members.
- Data Trust members are stakeholders who pay a membership fee and receive membership benefits, have a collaborative interest in pursuing shared goals, and who collectively play a role in the governance of the Data Trust.

- Data creators are those who create the data to be held in the Data Trust, including aggregated and derivative data.
- Data subjects are any person whose personal data is being collected, held or processed.
- Data stewards are independent representatives of the Data Trust deciding who has access to data, under what conditions and for whose benefit.
- Personal data is any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person ('data subject'); an identifiable natural person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier, or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person. Personal data may be defined differently in other jurisdictions.
- Stakeholders are the collective group of parties impacted by the Data Trust, including data providers, creators, users, beneficiaries, and third parties.

3.0 International Regulatory Landscape

The Open Access eBook Data Trust ("Data Trust") must have data to fulfill its purpose and will be populated with data from a wide variety of sources. Data will be licensed from commercial and noncommercial data providers, such as publishers and platforms, or scraped from public sources on the internet, such as social media sites. The Data Trust will be processing and storing large amounts of data on a continuous basis over the life of the Trust and will need to prepare for compliance with international privacy and data protection laws given the international scope of its proposed activities.

Some regulatory regimes have certain compliance exemptions for nonprofit entities, small businesses, or for statistical or scientific research purposes, but these exemptions vary on a country-by-country basis. Other countries have enacted more stringent data localization laws, which require data collected on a country's citizen to be retained and processed in that country.⁷

Overall, the regulatory risk for the core activities of the project will be low as the Data Trust aims to limit its processing and storage for its dashboard and analytics products to ebook usage data that is de-identified and non-personally identifiable. Operational data, however, has stricter requirements as it deals with heavily regulated sectors, including employment, marketing, and cookie tracking.

⁷ American Action Forum, *Impact of Data Localization Requirements on Commerce and Innovation* (June 2020), [Impact of Data Localization Requirements on Commerce and Innovation - AAF](#)

Figure 1: Regulatory Compliance Obligations Across Key Categories of Data Relevant to the Data Trust

Employment Data	Marketing Data	Legal Data	Curated & Customer Support Data	Cookies
HIGH	MEDIUM	LOW	LOW	HIGH

3.1 Jurisdictions Under Consideration

The data protection and privacy laws of the following four jurisdictions will be considered in this report: the United Kingdom, the United States of America, the Netherlands, and Australia. While the Data Trust will have to meet regulatory compliance for the countries of other global citizens interacting with the Data Trust, these four jurisdictions were selected for the report because:

- One or more data providers, founding partners of the Data Trust, or other major Data Trust stakeholders are located in the jurisdiction;
- Each jurisdiction has legal certainty and political stability;
- Each jurisdiction has an established and efficient legal system with significant legislation and common law that would provide critical guidance for dealing with a range of potential legal issues, including privacy and data protection.

3.2 Europe - General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)

The GDPR is the main privacy framework in Europe. The GDPR applies to all EU member states, including the Netherlands. Under the GDPR, organizations that intentionally offer goods and services to the European Union, or that monitor the behavior of EU citizens have strict privacy obligations.⁸ Therefore any activities of the Data Trust that involve the use, processing, or storage of the personal data of EU citizens or, more broadly, any processing of personal data that occurs within the EU would place the organization under the scope of GDPR.

The GDPR defines *personal data* as any information that directly or indirectly relates to a data subject, such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier, or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person.⁹

The Data Trust's key obligations for the European region and subsequently for the Netherlands, include the following:

⁸ EU General Data Protection Regulation, <https://iapp.org/resources/topics/eu-gdpr/#top>

⁹ GDPR Article 4, <https://gdpr-info.eu/art-4-gdpr/>

- **Limit** the collection of personal data to only the personal data needed for legitimate purposes or pursuant to a **lawful basis**;
- Use clear and specific **privacy statements** to notify data users in advance of the Data Trust's purposes for processing personal data;
- Obtain **consent** to process personal data in cases where permission is required;
- Use **appropriate technical measures** to protect personal data;
- Use **Standard Contractual Clauses** to ensure to counter parties that use or processing of personal data also have appropriate security measures in place;
- Respect **data subject rights** to access, correct, or delete any personal data held by the Data Trust.

3.3 Lawful Basis Is Required For Processing Data

In general, the GDPR prohibits the processing of personal data unless there is a *lawful basis* for processing that data. These bases include:

- **Consent** (The data subject has given consent to the processing of personal data for one or more specific purposes);
- **Contract** (Processing is necessary for the performance of a contract to which the data subject is party or in order to take steps at the request of the data subject prior to entering into a contract);
- **Legal Obligation** (Processing is necessary for compliance with a legal obligation to which the controller is subject);
- **Vital Interests** (Processing is necessary in order to protect the vital interests of the data subject or of another natural person);
- **Public Interest Task** (Processing is necessary for the performance of a task carried out in the public interest or in the exercise of official authority vested in the controller);
- **Legitimate Interests** (Processing is necessary for the purposes of the legitimate interests pursued by the controller or by a third party, except where such interests are overridden by the interests or fundamental rights and freedoms of the data subject which require protection of personal data, in particular where the data subject is a child.)¹⁰

Personal data that the Data Trust might encounter includes names, IP addresses, and scholar identification numbers such as digital object identifiers (DOIs) and ORCID IDs that are attached to ebooks and other scholarly output. However, any personal data that a data subject has manifestly made

¹⁰ GDPR Article 6, <https://gdpr-info.eu/art-6-gdpr/>

available to the public does not fall within the scope of GDPR.¹¹ At an organizational level, the Data Trust will be processing and storing the personal data of employees and data providers. From a technical standpoint, the IP addresses and tracking cookies might be collected on visitors to the Data Trust's website.

The "legitimate interest" basis is the most flexible basis for the Data Trust to process personal data. Processing for a legitimate interest does not require consent or a contractual agreement and can theoretically apply to any type of processing for any reasonable purpose. This basis applies whenever an organization uses personal data in a way that a data subject would expect. For example, collecting personal data for direct marketing purposes is considered a legitimate interest.¹² The Data Trust must follow a three-part test to determine whether personal data can be processed for a legitimate purpose. The three-part test consists of the following considerations:

- **Purpose:** The processing isn't required by law, but there is a clear benefit to it;
- **Necessity:** The processing is necessary for the purpose; and
- **Balance:** There is little risk that the processing would infringe the data subject's privacy or other rights.¹³

The Data Trust could also process personal data on a "consent" basis. Consent must be "freely given, specific, informed and unambiguous," and the data subject must give consent through a statement or affirmative action to be valid.¹⁴ Consent must also be obtained for each separate use of the data, and the data subject must also be able to withdraw consent at any time.¹⁵ The Data Trust can use opt-in mechanisms, such as cookie banners, clickwrap agreements, or unchecked boxes, all which require the data subject to affirmatively take an action.¹⁶ The Data Trust would also have to keep good records for handling consent withdrawals.

The collection and use of employment-related data might be obtained directly from a Data Trust employee on a "contractual basis," rather than on a consent basis, due to the presumed imbalance of power in the work environment.

3.4 GDPR - Data Processing Principles

¹¹ GDPR Article 9, <https://gdpr-info.eu/art-9-gdpr/>

¹² GDPR Recital 47, <https://www.privacy-regulation.eu/en/recital-47-GDPR.htm>

¹³ EU Preliminary Ruling (May 2017), [62016CJ0013 - EN - EUR-Lex](#); Legitimate Interests as a lawful basis, [Legitimate interest as a lawful basis | Data Protection](#); Data Protection Toolkit, [Data Protection Toolkit - Legitimate Interests Assessment & Template](#)

¹⁴ GDPR Article 4, <https://gdpr-info.eu/art-4-gdpr/>

¹⁵ GDPR Article 7, <https://gdpr-info.eu/art-7-gdpr/>

¹⁶ Data subjects would not have the option to opt-out, however, as these are essentially pre-ticked boxes, which are banned. [Pre-ticked boxes are not valid forms of consent under the GDPR](#)

Article 5 of the GDPR sets out the general principles for processing personal data. The Data Trust will have to document compliance with these principles as an overarching principle of accountability when handling personal data. The data processing principles include:

- lawfulness, fairness, and transparency;
- purpose limitation;
- data minimization;
- accuracy;
- storage limitation;
- integrity and confidentiality;
- accountability; and
- legal basis for processing.¹⁷

To comply with the purpose limitation principle, the Data Trust must demonstrate that personal data is being used only for the specific purposes communicated in the privacy policies. The data minimization principle would require the Data Trust to process personal data only in an amount to what is necessary for its purposes, which is most relevant to the employment, website, and organizational context. The accountability principle would require the Data Trust to conduct a data protection audit, keep accurate records of processing activities, provide staff training around the protection of personal data, and review and update privacy policies.

3.5 Consent and Special Categories of Personal Data

The Data Trust may encounter special categories of personal data during its corporate existence. For example, this type of data may surface in customer support responses, email communications with Data Trust members, or interviews with employees. Special categories of personal data include personal data revealing (a) racial origin; (b) ethnic origin; (c) political opinions, (d) religious or philosophical beliefs; (e) trade union membership; (f) genetic data or biometric data; and (g) data concerning a person's sex life or sexual orientation.¹⁸ Article 9(2) of the GDPR prohibits the processing of these special categories unless explicit consent is given by the data subject.

If special categories of information appear in social media data that is scraped for use in analytics, the information is exempt as it is assumed that the data subject made the information manifestly available to the public.¹⁹

3.6 Appropriate Measures - Pseudonymization, Anonymization, and SCCs

¹⁷ GDPR Article 5, <https://gdpr-info.eu/art-5-gdpr/>

¹⁸ GDPR Article 9, <https://gdpr-info.eu/art-9-gdpr/>

¹⁹ GDPR Article 9, <https://gdpr-info.eu/art-9-gdpr/>

The Data Trust should use appropriate measures to safeguard the data. From a technical standpoint, the pseudonymization and anonymization of data are key processes to implement and would help the Data Trust meet the principles of “data minimization” and “storage limitation.”²⁰ From a contractual standpoint, Standard Contractual Clauses, or SCCs, should be employed to legally ensure a safe cross-border data exchange.

Pseudonymization is the processing of personal data so that it can't be attributed to a specific data subject without the use of additional information, as long as such additional information is kept separately and subject to technical and organizational measures to ensure non-attribution to an identified or identifiable individual.²¹ Because of the residual risk of re-identifying de-identified data, pseudonymized data may be considered personal data if a person can use reasonable means to identify the data subject with the data. The Data Trust would therefore be responsible for taking account of all the possible ways that identification could happen while also weighing the costs and amount of time required for identification as objective factors in determining whether identification is reasonable.²² Performing this audit will inform the Data Trust about the need to further de-identify data and also provide evidence that the risk of disclosure has been properly considered.

Anonymization is the process of removing personal identifiers, both direct and indirect, that may lead to an individual being identified.²³ Data that is truly anonymized does not fall within the scope of GDPR and therefore becomes easy to use. While anonymized data would be the gold standard for ensuring that the Data Trust has a low privacy compliance burden, it would limit the Data Trust's ability to derive value and insight from the data. Furthermore, anonymizing all data, including operational data, would inhibit marketing efforts and the technical team's ability to personalize the user experience of the website and dashboards.

3.7 Data Subject Rights

The GDPR gives data subjects certain rights in their data. The Data Trust should notify data subjects in their privacy policy of these rights and be prepared to respond if a data subject exercises any of these rights. Rights relevant to the Data Trust include:

- Right of access to see the type of personal data that is processed about the data subject;
- Right of rectification to correct any information that is wrong;

²⁰ GDPR Article 5, [Article 5 EU General Data Protection Regulation \(EU-GDPR\). Privacy/Privazy according to plan.](#)

²¹ GDPR Article 4, <https://www.privacy-regulation.eu/en/article-4-definitions-GDPR.htm>

²² GDPR Recital 26, <https://www.privacy-regulation.eu/en/recital-26-GDPR.htm>

²³ IAPP, *Primer on Anonymization and Pseudonymization* (April 2017), [Looking to comply with GDPR? Here's a primer on anonymization and pseudonymization](#)

- Right to complain or file a complaint against the processing of personal data or against direct marketing;
- Right to be forgotten, which includes responding to requests for removing any personal data;
- Right to data portability, which includes the transfer of personal data to a third party, if technically possible; and
- Right to restriction of processing, which may be temporary in nature.

3.8 GDPR and the Research Exemption

While the Data Trust expressly notes that they would like to move beyond the research stage that is currently underway for the pilot Data Trust, it is important to note that the GDPR interprets research purposes in a “broad manner” and gives examples such as technological development and demonstration as well as privately funded research that may fall under an exemption.²⁴ While there is a lack of clarity regarding the research exemption in the *private* context, it is suggested that to qualify, the Data Trust may have to circulate freely its research and technology,²⁵ which it is not likely to happen given its business model aspirations.

3.9 Operationalizing GDPR Compliance

Understanding when GDPR is triggered is an important first step towards operationalizing GDPR compliance within the organization. For the Data Trust, the GDPR is triggered in three general instances:²⁶

- (a) if the Data Trust is located within the EU, then any activities that involve the **processing of personal data**, regardless of where the personal data is processed, would trigger GDPR compliance;
- (b) if the Data Trust is located outside of the EU, then any goods or services that the Data Trust offers within the EU would trigger GDPR compliance; and
- (c) if the Data Trust is located outside of the EU, then the monitoring of behavior of individuals in the EU would trigger GDPR compliance.

²⁴ GDPR Recital 159, <https://www.privacy-regulation.eu/en/recital-159-GDPR.htm>

²⁵ GDPR Article 179(1), [REGULATION \(EU\) 2016/ 679 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL - of 27 April 2016 - on the protecti](#); GDPR Article 89, <https://gdpr-info.eu/art-89-gdpr/>

²⁶ European Commission, *Who does the data protection law apply to?*, https://ec.europa.eu/info/law/law-topic/data-protection/reform/rules-business-and-organisations/application-regulation/who-does-data-protection-law-apply_en#:~:text=Answer,Answer,the%20data%20is%20processed%3B%20or

Within the context of GDPR, “processing” means:

Any operation or set of operations which is performed on personal data or on sets of personal data, whether or not by automated means, such as collection, recording, organization, structuring, storage, adaptation or alteration, retrieval, consultation, use, disclosure by transmission, dissemination or otherwise making available, alignment or combination, restriction, erasure or destruction.²⁷

This means that even when a Netherlands-based Data Trust collects, processes, and stores personal data in a region outside of the EU, GDPR is still triggered due to its jurisdictional location within the EU. This jurisdictional hook can be interpreted to mean that when an entity is located within the EU, the GDPR applies to *all data subjects*, regardless of citizenship.²⁸ Furthermore, because the GDPR covers all EU member states, an EU-based Data Trust must comply with GDPR requirements when engaging with other EU-based data users, data providers, and project partners.

If the Data Trust is located in the Netherlands (EU), some examples²⁹ of when the Data Trust might **process personal data** and therefore trigger GDPR compliance include:

- Conducting staff management and payroll administration for Data Trust employees;
- Using software to track, store, or evaluate employee data, such as travel expenses and emails;
- Managing employee and recruiting applications for HR purposes;
- Shredding documents containing personal data in the context of employment matters;
- Posting photos of individuals on the Data Trust website taken from membership or promotional events or conferences;
- Storing IP or MAC addresses from website visitors;
- Processing and storing usage data containing personal data;
- Storing system data, including log files and usernames / passwords for member dashboards and API access;
- Retaining data for dispute resolution, legal obligations, and to enforce contractual agreements; and
- Operating the website, tracking website analytics, and managing social media accounts.

When interacting with *data users*, a Netherlands-based Data Trust might **process personal data** and therefore have to comply with GDPR in the following situations:

²⁷ GDPR Article 4, <https://gdpr-info.eu/art-4-gdpr/>

²⁸ Bryan Cave Leighton Paisner, [GDPR’s Most Frequently Asked Questions: Does the GDPR apply to all EU citizens’ data?](#) (Feb. 2018).

²⁹ European Commission, What constitutes data processing?, https://ec.europa.eu/info/law/law-topic/data-protection/reform/what-constitutes-data-processing_en

- Processing contracts, such as membership agreements or API access agreements;
- Processing financial information of data users;
- Sending promotional emails³⁰ for sales and marketing outreach;
- Tracking data user cookies from website activities and engagement with tools, widgets, and services;
- Storing data user contact information;
- Sharing publicly-accessible governance information, including biographical and affiliation data of members and board members; and
- Managing and providing access to membership databases.

When interacting with *data providers*, an EU-based Data Trust might **process personal data** and therefore trigger GDPR compliance in the following situations:

- Processing legal contracts for data sharing, data licensing, and data transfers;
- Processing financial information of data providers;
- Transferring, importing, or exporting usage data containing personal data;
- Managing a customer relationship management (CRM) database;
- Storing backup or retention copies of data containing personal data; and
- Sharing publicly-accessible data provider information, including biographical and affiliation data, for member updates, marketing, and newsletters.

4.0 Netherlands

The Netherlands implemented the GDPR in 2018 and used its legislative powers to derogate from the GDPR in certain areas, which are set out in the Act Implementing the GDPR (“Dutch Act”).³¹ The supervisory authority for data protection in the Netherlands is the Dutch data protection authority (AP). The definition of personal data is equivalent to the GDPR version, and the requirements for processing special categories of personal data are also in alignment with the GDPR.

The territorial scope of the Dutch Act is similar to that of the GDPR and would apply to the processing of personal data for the activities of an EU-based organization, regardless of where the processing takes place in the EU. There are no national notification or registration requirements applicable under the Act.

4.1 Data Localization Requirements - Netherlands

³⁰ Direct marketing emails must also comply with the ePrivacy Directive. https://edps.europa.eu/data-protection/our-work/subjects/eprivacy-directive_en

³¹ White and Case, *GDPR Guide to National Implementation: Netherlands* (Nov. 2019), <https://www.whitecase.com/publications/article/gdpr-guide-national-implementation-netherlands>

There are no data localization requirements in the Netherlands.

4.2 Variations with GDPR - Netherlands

Variations between the GDPR and Dutch Act include the requirement that Data Protection Officers be bound to secrecy for any information found in a data subject's complaint or request, unless the data subject provides consent to the disclosure of the information.

Certain data processing activities in the Netherlands may also require a Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA).³² For the Data Trust, this means any large scale monitoring of employees, location data, communications data, or personal data that is used to monitor or influence behavior could fall under this requirement. Potential areas for consideration include the employment context, website visitors, and emails from internal and external stakeholders. The Data Trust may be able to leverage the help of project partners in the Netherlands who have already conducted a DPIA on similar activities.

4.3 Employment Data - Netherlands

The Data Trust would have no restrictions as to what kinds of data it can process as an employer as long as there is a good reason for doing so. Special categories of data are prohibited from processing unless an exception applies or explicit consent is given. This restriction includes health data, including any data related to an employee's illness, sick days, medication, or disability.

Data Trust employees will be working on an international basis and may be based in regions where data localization laws apply. The safest mechanisms for the cross-border transfer of personal data would be through the use of standard contractual clauses (SCCs), although transfers between the Netherlands and the US may see additional requirements in the future. Localization laws can be complied with through use of a public cloud service.

Because the Data Trust will have a duty to inform employees³³ about the collection in advance, an employee privacy notice should include all pertinent information related to the processing, collection, and transfer of data. The Data Trust should also ensure that data subjects maintain the right to review or request correction or removal of their information.

Certain record retention requirements apply to information received for prospective employees, tax-related information, or information that is subject to a legal obligation such as the performance of a

³² Data Protection Impact Assessment, <https://gdpr.eu/data-protection-impact-assessment-template/>

³³ Osborne Clarke, GDPR and HR - What will change in the Netherlands? (Oct. 2017), <https://www.osborneclarke.com/insights/gdpr-and-hr-what-will-change-in-the-netherlands/>

contract. The Data Trust would be able to process employee records according to a legitimate interest or contractual basis.

4.4 Marketing Data - Netherlands

Marketing is regulated in the Netherlands by both EU and Dutch law.³⁴ In particular, there are consent requirements for sending *unsolicited* emails or direct marketing messages sent on social media.

The Data Trust would be able to process personal data for marketing purposes on the basis of a legitimate interest. Furthermore, the Data Trust would not have to obtain consent when a data subject's contact details are obtained in the context of the sale of its product or services, and when the marketing in question is for similar products and services offered by the Data Trust.

Because data subjects have the right to object to the processing of their personal data for marketing purposes at any time,³⁵ the Data Trust would have to provide a way for its marketing audience to opt out from messaging, including newsletters. This “opt-out” notice must clearly and explicitly give the opportunity to opt-out, be free of charge and simple to execute, and be offered when contact details are collected and on every future communication with the data subject.

4.5 Legal Data - Netherlands

Legal data in possession by the Data Trust might include employment contracts, vendor contracts, or membership agreements. While the Netherlands has no specific regulations or restrictions concerning legal data, there may be confidentiality clauses or other contractual privacy provisions that would prevent the Data Trust from disclosing information to third parties.

4.6 Curated Data & Customer Support Data - Netherlands

Curated data and customer support data are not specifically addressed by Dutch law, however, if any personal data lingering in these categories are collected by the Data Trust, then the Data Trust must comply with GDPR-based notice and privacy policy requirements in addition to providing appropriate safeguards to the collection, storage, and transfer of data.

³⁴ ePrivacy Directive, https://edps.europa.eu/data-protection/our-work/subjects/eprivacy-directive_en; GDPR, <https://gdpr-info.eu/>, Telecommunications Act, <https://www.government.nl/documents/policy-notes/2012/06/07/dutch-telecommunications-act>; and Dutch Advertising Code, https://www.reclamecode.nl/wp-content/uploads/2018/10/SRCNRCENboekje_oktober2017.pdf.

³⁵ GDPR Article 21, <https://gdpr-info.eu/art-21-gdpr/>

Curated data, including derivative data and database contents, may be subject to intellectual property protection pursuant to copyright law and the Database Directive's³⁶ *sui generis* right. To qualify for protection, there must be “substantial investment” in terms of obtaining, verifying, and presenting the data, and “originality” related to the “selection and arrangement” of the data.³⁷ In situations where the data selection process is automated and developed without creative freedom, then there isn't sufficient originality.

If originality exists in the data arrangement of its database contents,³⁸ the Data Trust would have a legal right to pursue infringement claims in certain jurisdictions if all or a substantial part of the database's contents are extracted or made public without the Data Trust's permission. Database rights have a duration of 15 years unless the database is being continually updated with substantial changes.

4.7 Cookies - Netherlands

The Dutch AP refers to “cookies” as small files that a website provider places in the user's electronic equipment that can be used to collect or store information about a visit to the website or the device of the user. The Data Trust will likely use cookies to improve and customize the website and member dashboards.

The Data Trust must give clear notice about the retention period, purpose and intent of using any tracking cookies. This can easily be achieved with a cookie banner. Cookie walls are also not permitted because they do not allow a user to freely give consent. No consent is required for analytical cookies that count website visitors or functional cookies that are required for the website to work properly.

5.0 United Kingdom

With Brexit, the UK has implemented their own version of the GDPR, known as the UK GDPR.³⁹ Although the Brexit Withdrawal Agreement⁴⁰ allows for the amendment of UK data protection laws, no substantive changes have been made yet. In 2021, the European Commission issued a draft adequacy decision stating that UK law is “essentially equivalent” to that of the EU in most respects.⁴¹ An adequacy decision means that the EU has deemed a particular country's data protection laws as

³⁶ European Commission, *Protection of Databases*, <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/protection-databases#:~:text=The%20Directive%20protects%20databases%20by%20copyright%20if%20they%20are%20original.&text=This%20protection%20is%20known%20as,both%20analogue%20and%20digital%20databases>.

³⁷ *Football Dataco Ltd v Brittens Pools, Yahoo! UK Ltd and others* (2010).

³⁸ European Commission, [Database protection in the EU - Your Europe](#)

³⁹ European Parliament (Jan. 2021), [Brexit deal: how new EU-UK relations will affect you | News](#)

⁴⁰ European Parliament (Jan. 2020), [Brexit deal approved by the European Parliament | News | European Parliament](#)

⁴¹ National Law Review (Feb. 2021), [EU and UK Data Sharing: UK Adequacy Decision](#)

adequately providing protections for EU data subjects. The UK also retained the EU standard contractual clauses as a transfer mechanism.

As a nonprofit, the Data Trust would be exempt from paying a registration fee with the Information Commissioner's Office (ICO). However, as a benefit corporation, a small fee would be required.

5.1 Data Localization Requirements - UK

There are no data localization laws in the UK with the exception of a residency requirement for company accounting records that are stored outside of the UK. The 2020 EU-UK Trade Agreement included an agreement to refrain from enacting data localization laws that restrict cross-border data flows.⁴²

5.2 Data Processing - UK

The Data Trust may be required to conduct a Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA)⁴³ for certain activities, including (1) the use of innovative technology; (2) matching data or combining datasets from different sources; (3) collecting personal data from a source other than the individual without providing that individual with a privacy notice (“invisible processing”); and (4) tracking individuals' location or behavior, for example, through cookies.

5.3 Employment Data - UK

The specific obligations for processing and storing UK employment data are comparable to the Netherlands. The Data Trust will be able to process employment data on a number of lawful bases, including compliance with a legal obligation, performance of a contract, and for legitimate interests. The Data Trust will need to provide a privacy notice to employee candidates detailing how their data will be collected and processed. The Data Trust will also need to maintain processing records due to the probability of collecting data that falls within a special category, such as an employee's record of sick days.

5.4 Marketing Data - UK

Marketing regulations in the UK are similar to those in the Netherlands, however, the UK Trade and Cooperation Agreement (TCA) regulates *unsolicited* direct marketing communications and the consent

⁴² Hunton Andrews Kurth (Dec. 2020), [EU-UK Trade Deal: What It Means For Post-Brexit Data Flows](#)

⁴³ The test for determining the processing activities which require a DPIA under GDPR can be found under Article 35(1) of the GDPR. <https://gdpr-info.eu/art-35-gdpr/>

of data subjects.⁴⁴ The EU Privacy and Electronic Communications Regulations 2002⁴⁵ still applies to the UK, despite Brexit.

The Data Trust must obtain consent for *unsolicited* marketing, and consent must be clear and specific. Best practice includes mechanisms that invite the data subject to confirm consent while avoiding pre-checked opt-in boxes. Placing consent notice in the general terms and conditions is insufficient. The Data Trust is obligated to keep clear records of consent details and to ensure that individuals who withdraw consent are no longer contacted. Another best practice is creating a “do not email” list.

By contrast, no consent is required in the UK when personal data is processed for “legitimate interest” marketing purposes. This might include contact details that the Data Trust obtains in the context of a sale of its products or services when the marketing is for similar products and services offered by the Data Trust. Despite the absence of a consent requirement for this category of marketing data, the recipient must be given an easy and free way to opt-out of marketing communications.

5.5 Legal Data - UK

Legal data in possession by the Data Trust might include employment contracts, vendor contracts, or membership agreements. While the UK has no specific regulations or restrictions concerning legal data, there may be confidentiality clauses or other contractual privacy provisions that would prevent the Data Trust from disclosing information to third parties. The use of SCCs in contracts with data processors can ensure privacy compliance requirements.

5.6 Curated Data and Customer Support Data - UK

Curated data and customer support data are not specifically addressed by UK law, however, if any personal data lingering in these categories are collected by the Data Trust, then the Data Trust must comply with the UK GDPR notice and privacy policy requirements in addition to providing appropriate safeguards to the collection, storage, and transfer of data.

Curated data, including derivative data and database contents, created by the Data Trust may be subject to intellectual property protection. In the UK, *database rights*⁴⁶ are governed by the UK Copyright and Rights in Databases Regulations 1997.⁴⁷ The law defines a database as “a collection of independent works, data or other materials which are arranged in a systematic or methodical way and are

⁴⁴ The TCA has yet to be ratified. [The EU-UK Trade and Cooperation Agreement](#)

⁴⁵ ePrivacy Directive, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX%3A32002L0058>

⁴⁶ Pinsent Masons (Dec. 2019), [Database rights: the basics](#)

⁴⁷ CooleyGO, [What You Need to Know about UK Database Rights](#)

individually accessible by electronic or other means.”⁴⁸ Under this law, both the structure of the database and its contents would be protectable. To qualify for protection, there must be “substantial investment” in terms of financial, human, or technical resources, and “originality” related to the “selection and arrangement” of the data.⁴⁹ In situations where the data selection process is automated and developed without creative freedom, then there isn’t sufficient originality.

If originality exists in the database, the Data Trust would have a legal right to pursue infringement claims if all or a substantial part of the database’s contents are extracted or made public without the Data Trust’s permission.

5.7 Cookies - UK

The Data Trust would not be able to use cookies unless the dashboard or website user is given clear and comprehensive notice about the cookie use, and consent is freely given. Consent must be separate from other requests and cannot be added to privacy notices or lumped in with terms and conditions. Cookie walls are also prohibited. Contrary to the Netherlands, analytical cookies are not exempt from consent requirements.

6.0 United States

There is no general, comprehensive federal privacy regulation in the United States (US), however there are several privacy-related laws at the federal level that govern certain sector-specific data, such as telemarketing, video privacy, health information, financial information, and electronic communications. Privacy and data governance laws may apply at the state level, however many states do not have relevant legislation.

6.1 EU-US Privacy Shield

Until recently, the US participated in the Privacy Shield Framework with Switzerland and the EU, which allowed organizations to transfer personal data outside of the EU to certified US-based organizations. In July 2020, the Court of Justice of the European Union (CJEU) invalidated the Privacy Shield based on the fact that US intelligence services would have access to personal data. However, the CJEU stated that Standard Contractual Clauses (SCCs) in data transfer agreements remain valid.

The invalidation of the EU-US Privacy Shield would require the Data Trust to use SCCs in any data transfer agreements with EU counterparts to remain in compliance with EU law. Additional regulatory

⁴⁸[The Copyright and Rights in Databases Regulations 1997](#)

⁴⁹ *Football Dataco Ltd v Britten Pools, Yahoo! UK Ltd and others* (2010).

safeguards for EU-US transfers may also apply. European data providers would have additional burdens for contracting with a US-based Data Trust, including the requirement to conduct due diligence on the transfer to the United States. For this reason, data providers may be incentivized to contract with a Data Trust incorporated in a region that has an adequacy decision from the EU to avoid any additional regulatory burden.

6.2 Data Localization Requirements - US

There are no data localization laws in the United States. In fact, the US has historically sought to ban data localization requirements in trade agreements due to the restrictions placed on trade flows, data processing, and network management functions.⁵⁰

6.3 Delaware

At the state level, the most likely jurisdiction in the US for incorporation of the Data Trust is Delaware due to its business-friendly environment, recognized business court, and advanced collection of corporate case law. The Delaware Constitution of 1897 does not specifically reference a right to privacy, although it does have a similar type of Fourth Amendment right against unreasonable searches and seizures.⁵¹ However, the Delaware Supreme Court has recognized that Delaware ‘has a commitment to protecting the privacy of its citizens.’⁵²

In Delaware, PII means:

a consumer’s first name or first initial and last name in combination with any 1 of the following data elements that relate to the consumer, when either the name or the data elements are not encrypted:

Social Security number; passport number; driver’s license or state identification card number; insurance policy number; financial services account number; bank account number; credit card number; debit card number; tax or payroll information or confidential health-care information including all information relating to a patient’s health-care history; diagnosis condition, treatment; or evaluation obtained from a health-care provider who has treated the patient which explicitly or by implication identifies a particular patient.⁵³

⁵⁰ American Action Forum, *Impact of Data Localization Requirements on Commerce and Innovation* (June 2020), [Impact of Data Localization Requirements on Commerce and Innovation - AAF](#)

⁵¹ [The Delaware Constitution of 1897](#)

⁵² *Jones v. State*, 745 A.2d 856, 866 (Del. 1999).

⁵³ [6 Delaware Code § 5001C \(2019\) - Definitions. :: 2019 Delaware Code :: US Codes and Statutes :: US Law](#)

PII does not include information lawfully made available to the public from a government record or widely distributed media, including social media. Encryption is an adequate measure for processing and storing PII.

The Delaware Online Privacy and Protection Act (DOPPA) would require the Data Trust to conspicuously post privacy policies on the website when collecting PII due to its status as a platform operator.⁵⁴ The privacy policy should include the following:

- The types of PII being collected;
- The categories of third parties with whom the operator may share such information;
- A procedure for a user to review and request changes to that user's information;
- The effective date of the policy; and
- How the operator will notify users of changes to the policy.

6.4 Employment Data - Delaware

Under Delaware law, employees must be allowed to inspect their personnel files and document any disputed information in their records. If the Data Trust destroys any records containing employee PII, then the Data Trust would have to make all the PII unreadable or indecipherable.

With regards to employee communications, the Data Trust is prohibited from monitoring employee telephone, email, or internet access information unless there is clear notice of the monitoring policy. Likewise, the Data Trust would not be able to require an employee to disclose information related to social media accounts, including usernames and passwords.

Employee financial data, including tax and account numbers, is considered PII and therefore protected by Delaware law.

6.5 Marketing Data - Delaware

Delaware has no regulations or restrictions concerning marketing data that are relevant to the Data Trust.

6.6 Legal Data - Delaware

Legal data in possession by the Data Trust might include employment contracts, vendor contracts, or membership agreements. While Delaware has no specific regulations or restrictions concerning legal

⁵⁴ Proskauer, [Delaware Enacts Comprehensive Online Privacy Protection Law](#) (Nov. 2015).

data, there may be confidentiality clauses or other contractual privacy provisions that would prevent the Data Trust from disclosing information to third parties.

6.7 Curated Data & Customer Support Data - Delaware

The Data Trust will also have curated data and customer support data. Neither category is specifically addressed by Delaware law, however, if any PII exists in the data and is collected by the Data Trust, then the Data Trust must conspicuously post a detailed privacy policy when user PII data is collected. Further measures must be taken to protect the PII of site visitors and members from the EU and other countries that have more stringent privacy restrictions.

Curated data may be protected by intellectual property law, however a *sui generis* database right does not exist in the United States. Copyright protection⁵⁵ is given to compilations of data that are creatively selected and arranged, but this still allows users to extract data as long as they do not select and arrange the data in the same way as the protected version.

6.8 Cookies - Delaware

Unlike the EU which has specific laws governing the use of cookies, there is a patchwork of state and federal laws in the US that treat cookies as regulated personal information. The CCPA in California, for example, requires companies to disclose the use of cookies in their privacy policies. In Delaware, however, there are no laws regulating cookies and other unique personal identifiers.

7.0 Australia

The key legislation in Australia governing privacy and data protection is the Privacy Act and its Australian Privacy Principles (APPs) as well as the Privacy Regulation 2013. In 2020, the consumer data right (CDR) was introduced in the Competition and Consumer Act 2010 (CCA), which is currently limited to the banking industry with the expectation that other sectors will be integrated at a later date.

In Australia, “personal information” is defined as:

Information or an opinion about an identified individual or an individual who is reasonably identifiable (1) whether the information or opinion is true or not; and (2) whether the information or opinion is recorded in a material form or not.⁵⁶

⁵⁵ *Feist Publications, Inc. v. Rural Telephone Service Co.*, 499 U.S. 340 (1991).

⁵⁶ OAIC, [What is personal information?](#) — OAIC

Notably, the processing of de-identified or anonymous data is not covered by the Privacy Act/APPs. The scope of the application of APPs is broad and applies to all disclosures of personal information of Australian citizens to overseas recipients.

7.1 Data Localization Requirements - Australia

The data localization requirements relevant to the Data Trust in Australia are sector-specific. If the Data Trust processes health information within the employment context, that information cannot leave certain states, including New South Wales (NSW), Victoria, and Australian Capital Territory (ACT).

7.2 Exemptions - Australia

The Privacy Act and APPs apply to all private sector organizations. However, organizations, including all of their related corporate bodies, that have less than AUD 3 million (€ 1.9 mill) in annual total ordinary income are exempt. According to current business model projections, the Data Trust is not required to comply with the Australian Privacy Act and APPs as it is not considered an “organization” under the meaning of the Act.

Most universities in Australia are also exempt from federal privacy laws, even though state and local privacy laws may still apply. The Data Trust therefore would have a low privacy burden if hosted within a public Australian university. By contrast, if hosted within an Australian nonprofit with income that exceeds the current thresholds, the Data Trust may be pulled under the scope of the Privacy Act if the combined income of both organizations exceeds the threshold.

7.3 Best Practices - Australia

While the Data Trust has an exemption from compliance with Australia’s key privacy legislation, the absence of an adequacy decision in Australia means that the Data Trust must still meet certain requirements for international data transfers. Best practice⁵⁷ includes providing the following appropriate safeguards:

- Embed a culture of privacy that enables compliance;
- Appoint key roles and responsibilities for privacy management;
- Manage privacy obligations with other countries;
- Use agreements with standard contractual clauses (SCCs) and/or binding corporate rules (BCRs) if a multinational Data Trust approach is pursued;
- Implement risk management processes;
- Undertake privacy impact assessments for activities;

⁵⁷ Office of Australian Information Commissioner, [Privacy management framework: enabling compliance and encouraging good practice](#) (May 2015).

- Document compliance with privacy obligations;
- Ensure approved codes of conduct are in place, including privacy policies, and
- Obtain consent when required and where possible.

7.4 Employment Data - Australia

Despite the recognized exemption for the Data Trust, other privacy regulations may apply such as employment and tax-related TFN Rules.⁵⁸ TFN Rules relate to tax file numbers (TFN) and apply to any person or entity that holds employee records that contain such numbers. TFN information is information that connects a TFN with the identity of a particular individual, such as a database record that links a person's name and birthday with the person's TFN. The Data Trust would be permitted to disclose TFNs for the purpose of facilitating the payroll and tax process for employees.

When collecting TFN from employees, the Data Trust would have to comply with notice requirements under APP 5, and other related laws, including the Taxation Administration Act (TAA), the Income Tax Assessment Act 1936, and the Data-matching Program Act 1990.⁵⁹ The Data Trust would also have to take reasonable steps to securely destroy or permanently de-identify TFN information when there is no longer a purpose to process. Unauthorized use or disclosure of TFNs can be a breach of the TAA and the TFN Rule. However, as an exempt organization, the Data Trust would not have to comply with Australia's Notifiable Data Breach (NDB) scheme.⁶⁰

7.5 Legal Data - Australia

Legal data in possession by the Data Trust might include employment contracts, vendor contracts, or membership agreements. While the Data Trust is likely to be exempt from Australian privacy regulations, there may be confidentiality clauses or other contractual privacy provisions that would prevent the Data Trust from disclosing information to third parties.

7.6 Marketing Data - Australia

In Australia, marketing is regulated pursuant to the Australian Privacy Act and the Spam Act.⁶¹ When marketing by email or social media, the Data Trust cannot send *unsolicited* messages to its marketing audience unless the customer has provided consent. Consent may be either express or inferred,

⁵⁸ Privacy Act Section 17, <https://www.legislation.gov.au/Details/C2020C00025>

⁵⁹ Office of Australian Information Commissioner, *What is a TFN Recipient?*, <https://www.oaic.gov.au/privacy/guidance-and-advice/the-privacy-tax-file-number-rule-2015-and-the-protection-of-tax-file-number-information/#:~:text=What%20is%20a%20TFN%20recipient,record%20that%20contains%20TFN%20information> (Aug. 2015).

⁶⁰ Office of Australian Information Commissioner, [Part 4: Notifiable Data Breach \(NDB\) Scheme](#) — OAIC (July 2019).

⁶¹ [Spam Act](#) 2003

contrary to the UK and EU. The Spam Act offers an exception for charities that send “designated commercial electronic messages” that relate to the provision of their goods and services, which may apply to the Data Trust. Marketing emails must also contain accurate sender information and a simple unsubscribe option.⁶²

7.7 Curated Data & Customer Support Data - Australia

Curated data and customer support data are not specifically addressed by Australian law. Even if personal data exists in either category of data, no specific compliance is necessary for the processing of personal information given the Data Trust’s “small business” exemption. Other countries’ laws related to processing personal data, however, would still apply.

Curated data created by the Data Trust may be subject to intellectual property protection, including derivative data and database contents. Australia does not have any individual *sui generis* database right, but databases may be protected by copyright if they are original. To be “original,” the database must have involved “independent intellectual effort” and therefore any automatic compilation is unlikely to be protected.⁶³

7.8 Cookies - Australia

Personal information collected through the use of cookies may be regulated by the Privacy Act, even though cookies are not specifically addressed. However, the Data Trust’s “small business” exemption would remove any compliance burden from the Data Trust regarding cookie regulation, unless related to specific tax or employment issues.

8.0 Global Data Localization Laws

The Data Trust should expect to manage an international set of personal data given the geographically diverse base of website visitors, Data Trust members, vendors, and employees. Compliance with data localization laws varies widely depending on jurisdiction, but usually involves a government mandate that requires citizen data to be physically stored on servers located in the home country. The following countries have explicit data localization requirements: Russia, China, Kazakhstan, Nigeria, Indonesia, Vietnam, Malaysia, and Greece. Other countries have sector-specific requirements, such as for health or financial data, including: Canada, Turkey, Venezuela, Ukraine, Australia, and New Zealand.

For example, in Australia, health records must not leave the country. In New Zealand, electronic business and tax records must be stored locally.

⁶² [Spam Act](#), Sections 17 and 18

⁶³ *Telstra Corporation Limited v. Phone Directories Company* (2010).

The solution for dealing with the growing popularity of data localization laws is for the Data Trust to adopt a hybrid cloud solution.⁶⁴ A private cloud can be hosted locally to address security, compliance, connectivity, and performance concerns. A public cloud, such as Amazon Web Services and Microsoft Azure, offers scalability, cost effectiveness, and a simple way for data to be stored within specific countries that have data localization mandates. A hybrid cloud architecture would allow the Data Trust to communicate to members that their data does not leave the home country, which would eliminate the need to obtain consent for heavily restricted cross-border transfers.

9.0 EU Data Governance Act

In November 2020, the European Commission published its draft Data Governance Act (“draft Act”).⁶⁵ Some of the key findings of the draft Act includes new rules for the reuse of public sector data that would prohibit public sector bodies from entering into exclusive arrangements. There are also new rules that apply to the sharing of confidential data or data protected by intellectual property rights with a reuser who intends to engage in cross-border transfers of the data. Chapter III of the Act⁶⁶ discusses the possibility of a certification mechanism for trusted data intermediaries and introduces new rules for data sharing service providers that include a notification obligation, compliance framework, and the appointment of a legal representative.

The concept of data altruism is also introduced in the draft Act and proposes registration and monitoring for data altruism organizations. The draft Act would require data altruism organizations to operate on a nonprofit basis and place the data-sharing services in a separate, independent legal entity.⁶⁷

The current draft specifically applies to public sector bodies and does not apply to data held by cultural and educational establishments. While this legislation does not currently impact the Data Trust, it does raise an important consideration that a two-part entity structure, with data sharing services held in an independent legal entity, has not only received approval by European regulators but will soon be legally mandated.

10.0 Recommendation - Privacy Approach and Jurisdiction

⁶⁴ IBM, [How hybrid cloud solves data localization and regional compliance challenges - Cloud computing news](#) (July 2015); Deloitte, [Data privacy in the cloud](#) (2016).

⁶⁵ European Commission, European [Data Governance | Shaping Europe's digital future](#) (March 2021).

⁶⁶ Data Governance Act, [52020PC0767 - EN - EUR-Lex](#) (Nov. 2020).

⁶⁷ Data Governance Act, [52020PC0767 - EN - EUR-Lex](#) (Nov. 2020).

To comply with international privacy obligations, this report recommends taking a risk-based approach and focusing on regulations that are likely to be enforced, carry the steepest penalties, and have the highest risk of lawsuit. The laws of the European Union, Singapore, Japan, Brazil, and California are areas on which to focus.

As a startup, the Data Trust will need to meet its international compliance objectives in a cost-effective way. Recommendations include:

- Have a high level understanding of the data inventory by identifying broad categories of data that is flowing through the organization;
- Identify access controls and retention periods for data;
- Ensure the Data Trust is abiding by privacy policy commitments and confirm with project staff;
- Have appropriate data protection agreements in place with vendors and sub-vendors;
- Design a way to handle data subject access requests to handle customer complaints quickly;
- Build a hybrid cloud architecture for compliance with localization laws; and
- Display a cookie banner, scan for cookies, and design a repository for records processing and privacy impact assessments.

In selecting a jurisdiction to incorporate the Data Trust, the following factors were considered: (1) a country's legal system and relevant case law; (2) data privacy regime; (3) privacy compliance risks; (4) copyright; (5) database rights; (6) location of project staff; (7) location of technical infrastructure; (8) data localization requirements; and (9) tax considerations.

Based on this multi-factor analysis, the most attractive jurisdiction where the Data Trust should incorporate is the Netherlands. The Netherlands is a member of the European Union (EU), which has a robust, mature data privacy regime (GDPR) with substantial guidance already available to the public. While the compliance risk for the GDPR is one of the highest globally, being incorporated in the EU would ensure that the Data Trust is designed to meet the strictest privacy standards. Having these privacy protections in place will make it easier for the Data Trust to comply with less onerous national and state-based privacy frameworks. Furthermore, the EU has adequacy decisions with a select group of countries, which would facilitate cross-border data transfers. The EU also has both copyright laws and *sui generis* rights that would possibly give legal protection to the Data Trust's database contents. Location in the Netherlands would also facilitate potential partnerships with other Netherlands-based organizations, such as OAPEN and OA Switchboard.

Australia is an excellent alternative jurisdiction for incorporating the Data Trust. While there are no *sui generis* database rights in Australia, the Trust's data could retain some protection through copyright law, contracts, confidentiality provisions, codes of conduct, and membership agreements. The privacy compliance burden for Australia is very low, however the Data Trust would still have to adopt adequate safeguards for GDPR data subjects and citizens from other highly regulated regions. The technical

architecture and a large number of project staff are also located in Australia, which would ensure a smooth transition to the Data Trust startup phase.

While UK law is substantially similar to the Netherlands, the UK was not chosen due to the instability surrounding Brexit and the possibility that other changes in UK privacy law may be on the horizon. To date, the EU has not yet adopted an adequacy decision for the UK, and data transfers are being enabled by a bridging mechanism, which expires in June 2021.

	Legal System	Data Privacy Regime	Compliance Risk / Burden	Copyright	Database Rights	Location of Project Staff	Location of Physical Servers	Data Localization Requirements	Tax
Netherlands	Green	Green	Red	Green	Green	White	White	White	Green
UK	Green	Light Green	Red	Green	Green	Light Green	White	Light Pink	Green
USA	Green	Light Green	Light Red	Green	White	Green	White	White	Green
Australia	Green	Green	Light Red	Green	White	Green	Green	Light Red	Green

Legal Entity Analysis

11.0 Key Objectives for the Data Trust

The structure of a data trust can be created through legal mechanisms drawn from corporate law, trust law, and contract law. While many potential structures or combinations of structures exist, the preferred legal structure for a data trust is often determined on a case-by-case basis.⁶⁸ The preferred legal structure must also be attractive to all stakeholders to achieve the buy-in, cooperation, and active participation.

The Open Access eBook Data Trust also has the following legal and governance objectives, including:

- Operate a self-sustaining, community-owned, socially-conscious business model;
- Facilitate the sharing of data;
- Protect the interests of those with legal rights in the data;
- Create a governance framework that is neutral, independent, and governed by members;
- Ensure the collective management of the rights and interests of all members.

Based on these objectives, there are two legal entity forms that the Open Access eBook Data Trust should consider:

⁶⁸ Data Governance Act, [52020PC0767 - EN - EUR-Lex](#) (Nov. 2020).

- the nonprofit corporation; and
- the public benefit corporation (“PBC”).

These two entity forms reinforce the Data Trust’s not-for-profit or socially-conscious mission, focus on independence and transparency, and preferred framework for community governance. They also form the basis of other structures, including a parent-subsiary entity.

11.1 Common Benefits Between Nonprofits and Public Benefit Corporations

Nonprofits and public benefit corporations (PBCs) are preferred candidates for the Data Trust in that both have formal legal structures and entity attributes that include perpetual duration and the power to hold and transfer property, including data and intellectual property rights, in the corporate name. Both have legal personhood that give them the power to sue and be sued, and both can enter into a variety of contracts, including data sharing agreements and any contracts that support the operation and governance of an organization. Both entities also provide certain protections (“limited liability”) for members, directors, and officers from the corporation’s debts or liabilities. Legal personhood and power to contract would meet the Data Trust’s objective to protect the interest of those with legal rights in the data and to facilitate data sharing.

11.2 Nonprofit Corporation - Advantages and Drawbacks

11.2.1 Advantages

There are many types of nonprofit organizations. Relevant to the Data Trust is the public benefit and mutual benefit nonprofit types. Public benefit nonprofits are organized to engage in charitable, educational, health-related, or scientific work. Mutual benefit nonprofits are typically organized for the benefit of a membership group.

One of the main advantages to selecting the nonprofit model for the Data Trust is the immediate recognition by the public that the Trust has a purpose other than generating a profit and exists to further a socially-conscious mission. This public perception is vital for cultivating trust among stakeholders. The nonprofit model would dispel any distrust and controversy that historically has been associated with open access publishing projects that are structured for profit maximization.⁶⁹

⁶⁹ Hindawi and Knowledge Unlatched are controversial in the scholarly communications community because of their for-profit status. The open access publishing community supports the movement towards a non-profit model. Berger, M. *Everything You Wanted to Know About Predatory Publishing But Were Afraid to Ask* (2017), available at <http://www.ala.org/acrl/sites/ala.org/acrl/files/content/conferences/confsandpreconfs/2017/EverythingYouEverWantedtoKnowAboutPredatoryPublishing.pdf>

The nonprofit model also has advantages in terms of ownership and control. There is no equity ownership in most nonprofits,⁷⁰ and profits cannot be distributed to anyone in the Data Trust organization. The absence of these financial incentives means that the officers, directors, and members will be more committed to the collective goal of supporting the Data Trust's mission.

Nonprofits can also be governed by members, who would have specific voting rights to elect board members and vote on other important decisions. Governance by members would meet the nonprofit's goal of community governance. Given the diversity of stakeholders, including power, size, and resources, there must be a delicate balance in achieving trust through the delegation of voting rights. A single class of members is recommended to level the playing field for all stakeholders. However, it is likely that some larger data providers may ask for a larger share of voting rights in exchange for their participation. Managing decisions regarding voting rights will likely have to be decided at the community level or follow a voting allocation design similar to other nonprofits with large and diverse membership bases, such as CrossRef and Hathi Trust. Another advantage of the nonprofit membership model is that voting rights are not transferable, which means there will be no loss of control of the Data Trust to third parties.⁷¹ These factors meet the Data Trust's objective to become a community-owned and governed entity.

Nonprofit directors, who are elected by members, are required to meet certain fiduciary duties, including the obligation to be neutral and disinterested parties. These duties add transparency to the governance framework. To maintain independence and neutrality, it is recommended that directors are independent from the Data Trust, have independent relationships with Data Trust management, and are not selected from the membership base.

Another key advantage of nonprofits is that nonprofit law has a comprehensive statutory structure and body of case law that would be useful for Data Trust managers and advisors. Community governance can be further ingrained in organizational documents. For example, the articles of incorporation can specify that management makes decisions on behalf of community members. The bylaws can specify the powers, duties, and limitations of the Data Trust's board and its members that enhance trust among diverse members.

Nonprofits are also eligible for tax-exempt status, which would establish credibility with potential donors who would see that the organization has a legitimate public purpose and is publicly accountable.

⁷⁰ Limited liability companies can be structured for a nonprofit purpose.

⁷¹ The Data Trust would have to carefully consider how member classes and voting rights might affect the balance of interests among a diverse set of Trust stakeholders.

Tax-exempt status would also enable the Data Trust to receive funding from government entities and private donors.⁷²

From a regulatory perspective, nonprofits are exempt from significant data privacy obligations in certain jurisdictions, such as Australia and California.

11.2.2 Drawbacks

A potential drawback of some nonprofits is that in order to qualify for tax-exempt status under section 501(c)(3), the nonprofit must be organized exclusively for a permissible exempt purpose that benefits the public. Exempt purposes include scientific research and education. The Data Trust would have to ensure that it describes its purpose broadly enough to enable its proposed activities and also provide a benefit to the public, not just to its membership.⁷³

Another drawback is the difficulty in encouraging larger data providers to contribute data and become active in governance without incentives, such as additional voting rights or a financial return on investment. Also, as the Data Trust community grows, it may become difficult to identify independent board members who do not have conflicts with management, members, or broad membership groups.

11.3 Unrelated Business Taxable Income (UBTI)

Another consideration for the Data Trust and a major potential drawback is that some of its proposed activities may be classified as unrelated business income, which would therefore jeopardize the tax-exempt status of the nonprofit. The proposed activities of the Data Trust currently include the following revenue streams:⁷⁴

- Memberships;
- Dashboard subscriptions; and
- API access.

The income-generating activities of a charitable nonprofit should be consistent with its tax-exempt status and must be analyzed in relation to any unrelated business tax income issues (UBTI). As noted above, a scientific research exemption would be the most appropriate category to qualify for tax-exempt status. To this aim, the Data Trust would need a broadly written purpose clause in the Articles of Incorporation that permits the prospective revenue streams.

⁷² For example, the Mellon Foundation makes grants to organizations determined by the IRS to be 501(c)(3) charities. The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation, <https://mellon.org/grants/grantmaking-policies-and-guidelines/grantmaking-policies/>

⁷³ A 501(c)(6), on the other hand, can serve its membership base through services, advertising campaigns, and conferences or other events that promote the members' common business interests.

⁷⁴ OA eBook Data Trust Business Model Report

Charitable nonprofits can engage in some unrelated income-generating activities as long as the income from these activities do not exceed certain thresholds.⁷⁵ The first question to ask is whether the Data Trust’s activities fall within an exemption. To determine whether an income-generating activity is exempt, the IRS and US courts focus on whether the activity in question has a “commercial hue” or seems more like a commercial activity.⁷⁶ Memberships and dashboard subscriptions would probably fall within a general scientific research exemption as the data products and information directly benefit the public by supporting the scientific and scholarly discovery process.

However, without more information, the sale of API access and analytics services may constitute unrelated business income that may be so substantial⁷⁷ that it should be relocated into a separate legal entity or subsidiary. There are a few reasons for this conclusion.⁷⁸ First, the research and discovery data analytics tools are only available to their creators, which in this case include Data Trust members and data providers. Second, the Data Trust would retain ownership of a substantial portion of copyright (and possibly *sui generis* rights) in any data or derivative data, which will not be made available to the public. Third, the API/analytics services may be viewed as an activity that competes with for profit companies. Fourth, the Data Trust may be thinking about advertising these services among various stakeholders. Fifth, some of the Data Trust’s customers will be for-profit entities, such as commercial publishers. Finally, pricing policies and financial reserves are also important factors to consider. According to current financial models, API access services generate the most revenue for the Data Trust out of all of its revenue streams. In 2026, the Data Trust will also have a net profit, driven in large part by the API services revenue stream. On balance, these factors suggest that the sale of API services may be viewed as a large-scale and systematic profit-generating activity.⁷⁹

If UBTI makes up only 20-30% of the project’s gross income,⁸⁰ then that income is tax-exempt. However current financial models show that API revenues exceed this threshold, which may lead to a loss of tax-exempt status. For this reason, it is recommended that the Data Trust drop the analytics and API services, as currently described, into a wholly-owned subsidiary, such as benefit corporation, in order to freely pursue its profit-generating activities without limitation. Alternatively, the Data Trust could package API services as a “Premium Membership Benefit” and offer this package of services to members at prices that are set below cost, which may or may not be a financially sustainable proposition.

⁷⁵ Griffin, R., *Unrelated Business Income Tax Rules: Application to Membership and User Fees Charged by Auxiliary Organizations* (2009), <https://csuaoa.org/wp-content/uploads/2018/11/m9.pdf>

⁷⁶ *Airlie Foundation v. IRS*, D. D.C. No. 02-0785 (9/24/03)

⁷⁷ If unrelated business income comprises a "substantial" portion of an exempt organization's income, loss of tax-exempt status may result. *Indiana Retail Hardware Association v. U.S.*, 366 F.2d 998 (Ct. Cls. 1966).

⁷⁸ *BSW Group, Inc. v. Comm’r*, 70 T.C. 352, 358 (1978) (This case provides a multi-factor test to determine whether UBTI destroys the tax-exempt status of a nonprofit.)

⁷⁹ *Iowa State University of Science & Technology v. United States*

⁸⁰ Griffin, R., *Unrelated Business Income Tax Rules: Application to Membership and User Fees Charged by Auxiliary Organizations* (2009), <https://csuaoa.org/wp-content/uploads/2018/11/m9.pdf>

Deciding whether or not the API services will be unrelated business tax income is not a clear cut analysis, as case law indicates. Further case law analysis is therefore required, and an expert opinion is recommended.

12.0 Public Benefit Corporation - Advantages and Drawbacks

12.1 Advantages

Public benefit corporations (PBCs) have several advantages. A PBC is a for-profit corporation that has an obligation to pursue one or more public benefits. One advantage is the PBC's social benefit status, which would foster trust among Data Trust stakeholders. Many states give PBC shareholders the power to bring a "benefit enforcement proceeding" against the corporation if the public benefit is not being adequately pursued. PBCs also have to report on its overall social performance to shareholders, and PBC directors must consider the societal impacts of corporate activity, even when those activities go against shareholder value. These governance and accountability mechanisms would fulfill the Data Trust's goal of transparency⁸¹ and be attractive to stakeholders by providing them with a way to hold the Data Trust accountable for pursuing its socially-conscious mission.

PBC directors also have certain fiduciary duties to the Trust. The board of directors must balance several interests, including the interests of parties who might be affected by the corporation's conduct. These parties might include employees, data users, data providers, funders, and the broader scholarly communications community. This obligation to take into consideration the interests of a broad array of stakeholders would further establish accountability and transparency within the governance framework.

One major advantage of a PBC is its ability to engage in unlimited profitable activities, which supports the Data Trust's multiple revenue stream business model. Under a shareholder structure, profits would also be distributed to shareholders, creating financial incentives that might spur some (if not all) data providers to contribute data. However, deciding who is a shareholder and who is not would be challenging. If all members were shareholders, then distributions would also be potentially made to data users who have contributed less or no resources compared to data providers or funders.

12.2 Drawbacks

As noted above, the PBC shareholder scheme would be difficult to structure fairly. The Data Trust would have to be careful to ensure that there are no majority shareholders that could form within the membership base and take control of the organization. Funders and data providers may not be interested in participating if no additional incentives are provided, such as voting rights or larger share

⁸¹ Barnette, J., *What is a Benefit Corporation*, CooleyGO, <https://www.cooleygo.com/what-is-a-benefit-corporation/>

allocations. Equity ownership may also be attractive to outside investors, who may try to usurp control. Because shares would be transferable, there is a risk that an outside party could gain influence over decision-making and control. Unless all of the shares of the PBC are wholly-owned by a single shareholder who shares the mission of the Data Trust, these factors could likely damage the neutrality and independence of the governance model and impede the Data Trust's goal of stable, community-ownership and governance.

Another potential drawback of the PBC model is the organization's obligation to create value for shareholders. Although the risk is low, the PBC's hybrid purpose of public benefit and profit may seed distrust among the scholarly communication's community unless stakeholders are educated first about the PBC's social performance obligations and reporting requirements.

Because shareholders have standard corporate governance rights, the PBC would have the additional burden of keeping track of share ownership and voting rights. As the Trust grows in terms of the quantity and diversity of members (some who may require more shares to participate), the number of shareholders is likely to increase. Furthermore, the Data Trust's attempt to create an equitable allocation of shares may become a very complex process. The Trust would also have to track when shares are transferred and how transfers might skew the balance of interests for shareholders.

Tax liability is another drawback of PBCs. If a PBC elects to be taxed as a C corporation, it would be subject to federal income tax at the corporate level and its shareholders would be subject to income tax on profit that is distributed to them.⁸² If the PBC elects to be taxed as an S corporation, income would pass through to shareholders. PBCs would also not be eligible to receive donations that are considered tax deductible contributions, including grants.

13.0 Recommendation

It is recommended that the Data Trust adopt a two-part "Parent-Sub" entity structure, which achieves the Data Trust's core objectives, supports its proposed business model, and addresses stakeholder concerns regarding independence between open standards creation and data services. To structure this entity, a 501(c)(3) nonprofit becomes the parent corporation and a public benefit corporation (PBC) is organized as the subsidiary that is wholly-owned by the nonprofit. Functionally, the nonprofit would act as the operating entity and collectively manage open data standards and governance on behalf of members. The subsidiary would act as the fundraising entity that generates revenue from various business streams, including shared data services.

⁸²Wolters Kluwer, *Should I Form a Benefit Corporation or a Nonprofit? - Five Differences to Consider*, <https://www.wolterskluwer.com/en/solutions/ct-corporation/should-i-form-a-benefit-corporation-or-a-nonprofit#:~:text=Taxation,on%20profits%20distributed%20to%20them>.

13.1 The Parent-Sub Entity

The two-part entity structure has many advantages. This structure highlights the independence between the organizational functions of data standardization (and storage) and data analysis that have been perceived to be in conflict.⁸³ The two entities for this structure also have a transparent, independent governance framework and can be formed for a prosocial purpose to ensure that external and internal stakeholders view the Data Trust as a trusted agent. Because the nonprofit is the only shareholder of the subsidiary, both entities are community-owned and community-governed. The single shareholder setup would also prevent loss of control from outside investors and third parties unless the nonprofit elects to divest of its shares in the subsidiary. Keeping track of voting rights and share ownership for the subsidiary would not be an issue.

As controlling shareholder, the nonprofit could also appoint an independent board of directors for the subsidiary so that it maintains its neutrality and independence. The subsidiary should not use a board composition that is identical to the parent so that the profit-generating activities are not attributed to the parent.

The two-part entity structure also makes sense for tax and control considerations. The Data Trust's proposed sale of API/analytics services or subscription services may create unintended UBTI. Therefore if the Data Trust was set up as a single, centralized nonprofit entity, the production of UBTI may jeopardize the Trust's tax-exempt status. By dropping its profit-making services into a wholly-owned subsidiary, the Data Trust would be able to continue benefiting from grants and membership fees at the parent level and generate unlimited income at the subsidiary level. In the event of liquidation of the subsidiary, any remaining proceeds would be distributed to the nonprofit as the sole member. The nonprofit would also be insulated from any liabilities arising from new activities of the Data Trust subsidiary.

With any entity, there are disadvantages. Because charitable funding and grants should remain at the parent level, the parent nonprofit would need enough non-charitable assets to initially capitalize the subsidiary, which might come from a bridge loan. There are also start up costs and the ongoing costs of maintenance of two separate entities. Becoming the subsidiary of an existing nonprofit would address both of these issues.

⁸³ "A standard is independent of any single institution or manufacturer, and to which users may propose amendments." (Poutain, 2003).

If the profit-generating activities of the Data Trust are not considered UBTI, then forming the Data Trust as a single, centralized public benefit corporation would still be at risk of loss of control and independence due to the nature of a public benefit corporation's transferable shares.

13.2 Alternate Recommendation

In the absence of disqualifying UBTI, forming the Data Trust as a single, centralized nonprofit entity or merging within an existing nonprofit entity, such as OAPEN, is an alternate recommendation. All of the advantages of nonprofits discussed in section 11.2.1 would be consistent with this alternate recommendation. Furthermore, merging with an existing nonprofit has the added benefits of shared resources and privacy compliance expertise. Some potential nonprofit partners may also have provisions or change of control clauses that only allow mergers with other nonprofits.

Other governance and legal tools should also be used to meet the Data Trust's objectives. These might include a code of conduct, ethics and privacy policies, membership rules, contracts, and a conflict of interest policy.

13.3 Winding Up

As noted above, in the event of liquidation of the subsidiary in the parent-sub entity structure, any remaining proceeds would be distributed to the nonprofit as the sole member, after any creditors are paid. If the Data Trust decides to pursue the 501(c)(3) charitable nonprofit route, then distribution of assets may need to go to other 501(c)(3) nonprofits. For mutual benefit nonprofits, it may be permissible to transfer assets to the nonprofit's members if instructed by the articles or bylaws.

It is recommended that the Data Trust keep track of data and intellectual property ownership, data licenses, and data sharing agreements to determine where and how data assets could be distributed or returned, if necessary, during dissolution. Clearly specifying these outcomes in contracts and licenses with data providers may also prevent future disputes.

14.0 Incorporating a Data Trust in the Netherlands

To emulate the parent-subsidary model in the Netherlands, the Data Trust could consider incorporating an ANBI Foundation or "*stichting*," which is a close equivalent to the American 501(c)(3). ANBI refers to a Dutch entity's tax exempt status. Foundations in the Netherlands do not have members, but an independent governance structure can be replicated by appointing an independent board and a supervisory board, called the Council of Members or Controlling Board of Trustees. A Foundation can be a shareholder in a corporation or a subsidiary, and may develop business activities through subsidiaries.

While the public benefit corporation does not exist in the Netherlands, the Data Trust could incorporate a BV, which is equivalent to an American LLC. A BV does not have any startup capitalization requirements, which is an advantage over the Dutch NV (C corporation). The Data Trust could also obtain a B Corp certification to further signal its prosocial mission to the Data Trust community. Alternatively, because Dutch Foundations are eligible to earn profits and engage in commercial activities, the subsidiary may also be set up as a Foundation, unless Dutch tax rules stipulate that the Foundation cannot earn revenue above a threshold amount that transforms it into a profit-making enterprise.